

Provisions of Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal According to the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 26, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 11, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Civil, Judgment, Procedures Law</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4317354</p>	<p><i>The current study approached the demonstration of a clear picture on the extent of applying the concept of the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal to include the form of the suit and its description, the appreciation of the evidence and the correction of the physical mistakes denoted in the judgment of the first degree court if the latter shall not have corrected the same before appealing the judgment issued by it as well as the interpretation of the judicial judgment set as being ambiguous or confusing which would result in an issue upon execution in addition to demonstrating the practical and legal issues raised by the concept of the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal in light of the absence of explicit provisions provided by the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law to regulate the same.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The challenge by the means of appeal stands to be the practical one whereby the legislator applies the principle of litigation through two stages by providing the opportunity for the litigants to obtain a more fair judgment which is a challenge means that may not be entered more than once to avoid prolonging the litigation and to put an end to disputes for which the appeal rulings may not be appealed.

In fact, and promptly after challenging the order issued by the first degree court through the appeal, yet a set of effects are generated by the devolutive effect of appeal in what is known as the Legal Regulation of Appeal, i.e. the dispute ruled by the first degree court, and upon raising the appeal, shall be referred to the second degree court within the scope of the matters appealed since appeal, and on one hand, refers only the issues and motions submitted and ruled by the first degree court to the second degree court and on the other, it refers the matters appealed out of the judgment issued by the first degree court to the second degree one.

In fact, and for the second degree court to be able to re-judge the subject matter of the case in which the judgment challenged was issued by the first degree court by appeal, then it shall have the powers enabling it to do so. Hence, the devolutive effect of appeal vests the said powers upon the second degree court in terms of subject matter of the case challenged by the judgment issued in it of all of its aspects whether being related to the incidents or the applicability of the law just like the first degree court.

Actually, the concept of the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal, and in the absence of explicit legal texts regulating its provisions by the Jordanian Legislator, raises a set of practical and legal issues at the same time whether in terms of the legislative formulating, the interpretation of the legal texts regulating the procedures of challenge before the Appeal Court or in terms of the extent of observance of the judicial tribunals to apply the said texts or otherwise sound understanding of the same since resubmitting the dispute once again before the Appeal Court, in its capacity as a second degree court, necessitates stating at the specific framework of the authority of the Appeal Court on the basis of which it shall study and review the file of the case referred to it in order for it to have the authority to reconsider the case and state at its legal opinion concerning the subject matter of the case. Hence, the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal vests the Court of Appeal with the same power and authority vested upon the first degree court whereby the devolutive effect of appeal extends to include the form of the case and its description, the appreciation of the evidence and to the correction of the physical mistakes denoted by the judgment issued therein if the latter shall not have corrected the same before challenging the judgment issued by it as well as the interpretation of the court ruling.

In fact, studying the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal raises several questions including whether it is possible for the devolutive effect of appeal to extend to the form of the case and its description, the appreciation of the evidence and to the correction of the physical mistakes denoted by the judgment issued therein if the latter

shall not have corrected the same before challenging the judgment issued by it as well as the interpretation of the court ruling issued by the first degree characterized as being ambiguous to an extent hindering its execution?.

The methodology and division of the study:

The current study shall adopt the analytical and comparative methods by analyzing the legal texts in addition to approaching the relative legal provisions and concluding the objectives of the same guided by the views of jurisprudence and judiciary. Hence, we shall divide the subject matter of the study as follows:

First Section: the Extension of the Devolutive effect of the Case to its Form and Description.

Second Section: the Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Appreciate the Evidence.

Third Section: the Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Correct the Physical mistake.

Fourth Section: the Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Interpret the Judicial Ruling.

First Section

The Extension of Devolutive Effect of the Case to its Form and Description

The devolutive effect of appeal leads to its extension to the sound description of the cases regardless of the description concluded by the first degree court as the appeal court may confer the right legal conditioning to the case and determine the right legal provision applicable to the incidents of the case whereby it shall not cause the adversaries to lose any degree of the litigation as it is established by judiciary that the court is not bound to be restricted to the legal conditioning described by the parties for their case and that the cause of the case and the claim of the same is different from the legal conditioning as the determination of the legal ground of the case and its conditioning is of the core jurisdiction of the courts for which the court, and on view of the evidence submitted in the case, adopts the applicable rule out of the law provided that it shall fall within the scope of the incidents and demands set in the causes of the case.

Accordingly, the Jordanian Cassation Court ruled by a ruling denoting that: ((1- It is established according to the jurisprudence that the plaintiff elaborates the incidents of his/its case while the court conditions the said case in accordance with the facts established to it out of the evidence submitted in the case. In fact, the plaintiffs/the respondents in this case filed this case in the matter of banning opposition and a claim of the common rent while the court, and in light of the matters established to it to the effect that the possession of the defendant is a legal one on the property, then the case here is a leased vacating and a claim of rents payable according to the contract concluded by the court as being effective towards the respondents. Hence, and as the appeal court, and as a subject court, arrived at such conclusion in a sound and acceptable way based on the evidence submitted in the case including the statements set by the parties of the case in its minutes, then its ruling has been true.)).

Further, the devolutive effect of appeal extends to the form of the case for which, and in case it has been shown to the Appeal Court that the challenged judgment issued by the first degree court included an order to the effect of ceasing the case temporarily while the adversarial was untrue out of the death of the defendant, then the Appeal Court would rule for the invalidity of the ruling for ceasing the case being issued concerning an untrue adversarial without considering the same as wasting a degree of the litigation.

Second Section

The Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Appreciate the Evidence

The Jordanian Legislator determined the methods of proving in the Civil Law and the Evidences Law as being, namely: writing, testimony, case laws, acknowledgment, oath, inspection and experience

In fact, the Jordanian Legislator stated at the conditions for accepting each of the said methods according to the essence of the case and the nature of the incidents sought to be asserted for which it necessitated the writing in establishing the financial acts which value exceeds one hundred Dinars while allowing proving through testimonies and case laws in some cases and business. Further, the Legislator granted the first degree court, and as a subject court, a positive role in proving concerning establishing the physical incidents and the commercial transactions in addition to appreciating the assertion by the testimony of witnesses and causing an evidence to overrule another in addition to appreciating the need to consult with experts, devising the case laws and to

decide to what extension of necessity should the expert's report be adopted or either to deny it in full or in part and to estimate the extension to necessarily address the integral oath and adopt the result of the same.

Further, the Jordanian Legislator, and through the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law, vested the right upon the subject court to interrogate the adversaries concerning the matters necessary to settle the case and to instruct any party to exhibit any documents being in his/its hands or under his/its control as it shall deem necessary to settle the dispute and to address any questions to the witness after the adversaries shall be done with the interrogation and questioning of the witness as well as calling upon any witness whose testimony was heard before to be interrogated once again.

Hence, the first degree court has the absolute discretion to accept the evidence, weigh, review and extract the incidents therefrom in a sound way based on the evidence submitted according to articles (33, 34) of the Jordanian Evidences Law without being subject to the control of the Cassation Court unless the incidents shall have been extracted unsoundly being of no support by the evidence submitted and that there has been an explicit breach against the facts and the law.

However, the Appeal Court has the right to monitor the first degree court in that regard according to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal to appreciating the evidence, otherwise it shall have wasted the said evidences even if the extraction made by the first degree court out of the said evidences has not sound and of an origin established by the papers of the case. Further, and in case the first degree court erred in its weighing for the evidences submitted before it, yet the Appeal Court may reweigh the same, appreciate and adopt the said evidences and rule in the appeal adversarial according to the conclusion arrived at by it.

Accordingly, one of the rulings of the Jordanian Cassation Court denoted that: ((... 4- The Appeal Court has the authority to weigh the evidences and may cause its convictions to substitute those of the first degree court while entertaining the appeal or weighing the evidence and that the Appeal Court, and as a subject court, is entitled to appreciate and weigh the evidence as well as overweighing an evidence over another according to articles (33, 34) of the Evidences Law...)).

Third Section

The Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Correct the Physical Mistake

The first and second paragraphs of article (168) of the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law approached the rules of correcting the pure physical and calculation mistakes made in rulings, e.g. the mistakes in the names of the adversaries or the summation when calculating the amounts payable.

In fact, it stated that the court concerned with the correction is the court that issued the judgment whether being a magistrate's, first instant or appeal court. Further, that the correction shall be made by a decision issued by the court itself or upon the demand of one adversary while the decision may be challenged whether being for the rejection of the correction request or upon the acceptance of the correction request if I shall acted beyond the correction when the same shall extend to amending its previous judgment and changing its content after having been done with its jurisdiction in its regard.

Further, the judgment may not be challenged by the means of appeal set only for its physical correction as the physical mistake is not fit by itself as a cause for appeal but, however, and as the devolutive effect of appeal transfers the subject matter of the dispute to the Appeal Court and it shall be after submitting it together with its legal grounds and factual evidences, then the Appeal Court, and pursuant to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal in case of challenging the judgment for other than the physical mistake, yet it may rectify the physical mistakes shown in the appealed order since the first degree court issuing the same, and in this case, loses the right to correct the same after which the said right turns to be for the appeal court.

Accordingly, and one of its rulings, the Jordanian Cassation Court ruled as follows: ((Since the case was filed before the first degree court in the right way in the name of the plaintiff/Hashem ... in his capacity as being the attorney of Arkan ... but, however, the first degree court caused the name of the attorney Hashem to be included in the judgment issued by it ... without referring to him as being the attorney of Arkan ... by way of omission and mistake which does not cause the other adversary to acquire a right and which mistake has been rectified by the Appeal Court which included the name and capacity of the plaintiff in the right way, then this cause shall be rejected).

Fourth Section

The Extension of the Devolutive Effect of Appeal to Interpret the Judicial Ruling

The judge, and when he is about to issue his judgment in the case presented to him, shall observe that the judgment rendered shall become enforceable by observing that it meets the basic data set by the legislator on one part and its being issued clearly away from any ambiguity on the other. In fact, the interpretation of the court judgment is concentrated on the determination of the appreciation done by the judge being included in the judgment, the field of the said determination done in the scope of the elements that constitute the said judgment apart from the intention and discretion of the judge issuing the same and provided that the principle of interpretation shall be based on the determination of the appreciation contained in the judgment.

In fact, and even that the Jordanian Legislator vested the authority upon the execution president to request a clarification from the court that issue the judgment concerning the ambiguity denoted therein according to the provision of article (17) of the Execution Law No. (25) of 2007 and amendments thereof which stated that: ((The president may seek a clarification from the court that issued the judgment about the ambiguity denoted therein)), yet, the provisions of the said interpretation were not set in the Civil Procedures Law whether concerning the manner of asking for the interpretation, i.e. the procedures of the same or the matters related to the authority of the court that issued the judgment in terms of the interpretation and the scope of the said authority or the limits of the said interpretation and the legal effect resulted for having the court exceeded its authority in the interpretation. In fact, the provision of article (17) of the Execution Law has been the only one for the Jordanian Legislator who referred to the interpretation of the court judgment set as being ambiguous through the request to be made by the execution president for the issuing court to make clarification

In fact, the interpretation of the court judgment is just like its correction in terms of not being fit itself to stand as a cause to challenge the judgment. Actually, and according to the provision of article (17) of the Execution Law referred to above, then we find that it made the competence to interpret the court judgment set as being ambiguous for the court that issued the judgment, the subject matter of the interpretation considering it as being the most capable among the other courts to clarify any ambiguity therein. Hence, it is envisaged to have ambiguity committed by all the justice courts as the magistrate's or the first instant court may issue a judgment denoted as being confusing and ambiguous in the case heard within its jurisdiction when it shall have the objective and local jurisdiction to decide in the petition submitted to interpret the said judgment. However, the Appeal Court may be the one that issued the confusing or ambiguous judgment when it shall be the competent to interpret it. Yet, and in case the judgment issued by the first degree court shall be challenged while it is being set as being ambiguous, then the said challenge shall ban the submitting of a petition for interpretation to the court that issued the judgment considering that the judgment has been appealed and turned to be a subject to be heard by the Appeal Court for which it is probable either to be rescinded in full or be amended for which the interest to interpret turns to be null. Accordingly, and in case the Appeal Court issues a judgment that contains a confirmation of the order of the first degree court, then, and pursuant to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal, then the jurisdiction to interpret the ambiguous judgment shall pass to the Appeal Court for which it shall be competent to interpret the ambiguity set in the judgment while in case it rescinds the judgment or amend it in a way removing the ambiguity,, then there shall be no need to interpret the ambiguity in the said judgment either in case it amends the judgment or issued a one denoted as being ambiguous when it shall be the competent to interpret it according to the general rule.

Conclusion

In this study, we approached the provisions of the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal which arrived at several findings and recommendations as follows:

First: the findings:

1- The devolutive effect of appeal results in its extension to include the conditioning of the case in the right way regardless of the conditioning concluded by the first degree court as the Appeal Court is entitled to describe the case by the right legal conditioning and to determine the right legal provision applicable to the incidents of the case whereby it shall not waste any degree of litigation for the adversaries.

2- The Appeal Court has the right to monitor the first degree court that has the absolute discretion to accept the evidence, weigh, review and extract the incidents therefrom in a sound way based on the evidence submitted according to articles (33, 34) of the Jordanian Evidences Law according to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal to include appreciating the evidence and otherwise, it shall have wasted the said evidences unless the extraction made by the first degree court out of the said evidences has been sound and based on a the papers of

the case. Further, and in case the first degree court shall err in weighing the evidences submitted before it, yet the Appeal Court may reweigh, appreciate, adopt and judge in the appeal adversarial as it concludes.

3- The Appeal Court, and pursuant to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal, and in case the judgment is challenged for other than the physical mistake, may rectify the physical mistakes set in the appealed order as the first degree court that issued the same shall in this case lose the right to correct it which turns to be the right of the appeal court.

4- If the Appeal Court shall issue an order denoting confirming the judgment of the first degree court, then, and pursuant to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal, the jurisdiction to interpret the ambiguous judgment shall pass to the Appeal Court whereby it shall be the competent to interpret the ambiguity set in the said order while in case it rescinded or amended the same by away removing the ambiguity, then the interpretation of the same shall be no longer needed. However, and in case it shall amend the judgment or rescind it and issued a judgment in the subject being set as ambiguous, then it shall be the competent one to interpret it according to the general rule.

Second: the recommendations:

This study concluded several recommendations which we hope that the Jordanian Legislator shall adopt being as follows:

1- To cause the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law to explicitly provide that the appeal transfer the case in its status as being before the issuance of the appealed order as for the matters appealed only as the case of the provision of article (232) of the Egyptian Civil & Commercial Pleadings Law.

2- The Jordanian Legislator shall regulate the provisions of interpretation of the court judgment in the Civil Procedures Law whether concerning the manner of applying to interpret any of its procedures or the matters related to the authority of the court issuing the judgment to interpret, the scope of the said authority or the limits of the said interpretation and the legal effect resulted from having the court exceeded its authority to interpret in addition to the explicit providing for the authority of the Appeal Court to interpret the court judgment issued by the first degree court if the Appeal Court shall have issued a judgment containing a confirmation for the judgment of the first degree court.

3- To cause the Jordanian Civil Procedures Law to explicitly provide to the effect that the Appeal Court, and pursuant to the extension of the devolutive effect of appeal, may rectify any physical mistakes set in the appealed judgment if the same shall be challenged for other than the physical mistake as the first degree court issuing the same, and in this case, turns to be on no right to correct it while the said right turns to be of the Appeal Court.

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